

FORMATION OF MUSICAL PROFESSIONAL STUDENTS USING DIGITAL ART-PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *To create a high-quality and dynamic lesson, a music teacher in modern conditions can freely use digital services and specialized tools to provide lessons. A subject teacher—in our case, a music teacher—is required to be competent in using not only general pedagogical services, but also the ability to use specialized, professional digital resources and tools in professional activities.*

Keywords: *teacher-musician, digital resources, digital art-pedagogical technologies, music education, pedagogical modeling.*

Introduction. In order to create small musical structures, quickly transpose musical material of existing works into other keys, adapt professional scores for educational purposes at a university, as well as teach students the basics of musical notation with visualization and listening to musical material, the teacher needs to develop skills in the use of specialized digital resources. To ensure performing activities (learning vocal and choral compositions in lessons) in the absence or poor technical condition of an acoustic musical instrument, it is important to develop skills in using the tools and capabilities of virtual musical instruments. This requires the formation of new competencies focused on the effective use of digital art-pedagogical technologies in the educational process in creative profile programs, in this case in the “Music” profile. The process of teaching music in a university requires teachers to not only perform performing activities, but also work with professional digital services and resources. In connection with the above, professional competence of a teacher is required in the use of music editors, virtual musical instruments, specialized digital instruments and the introduction of creation products into the educational process in a university setting.

In the context of the modern socio-cultural space, society needs professionals who are fluent in the field of culture and art, who possess the means of creative direction in this area: playing a musical instrument, mastering the voice, and who are also able to put into practice the competencies that are in demand in the digital space. There is a need for teacher-musicians of a new quality, focused on prompt response in the conditions of changes occurring in modern science and technology. Teachers are required who can effectively solve assigned tasks using the skills developed during their professional training at a university. The practical application of digital art-pedagogical technologies by a musician teacher in the educational process is necessary when working with students.

Main part. The analysis of pedagogical research revealed the following: at the moment there is no stable opinion regarding the concept of “professional competence of university music students in the field of application of digital art-pedagogical technologies”, however, the components of this concept discussed in the previous paragraphs (professional competence of a teacher, teacher-musician and information competence of a teacher, teacher-musician) have numerous interpretations and interpretations. In the area of the problem under study, we believe it

is necessary to consider, analyze, reveal and clarify the concept of “professional competence of university music students in the field of application of digital art-pedagogical technologies.” To do this, we consider it advisable to begin researching the texts of the state’s regulatory documents, as well as the texts of international documents.

To increase the level of efficiency, a specialist in any field of professional activity needs to constantly improve and develop, mastering an increasing amount of necessary information in the subject area in which he realizes himself. In this regard, fluency in information systems may be a necessary condition for increasing the level of professional skills.

“At the moment, digital technologies are being widely introduced and used in various fields and areas of knowledge: engineering, economics, medicine, but the field of music pedagogy remains not fully covered, although, as mentioned earlier, potential employers have identical requirements in the field of developing competencies in areas of digital and information component”.

The issues of professional training of music teachers in the context of modern social transformations, in the context of the rapid development of technology, currently represent an incompletely resolved problem. Traditional forms of training are aimed at solid assimilation of knowledge in professional activities. Modern approaches to organizing the process of professional training of a specialist are aimed at developing the creative personality of the graduate, capable of freely solving any professional problems. The readiness of a teacher-musician is determined by his ability to develop and implement cultural and educational programs, to carry out presentation activities in the field of culture and education, the ability to think creatively and creatively, to take initiative, in the conditions of a modern information society, saturated with innovative technologies. Preparing future cultural specialists for professional and creative development is relevant at the stage of studying at a university.

A feature of the professional and creative development of a musician teacher is the process of self-realization of a future cultural specialist through involvement in the world of art and the space of cultural values. The basis of professional and creative development are the forms and methods of mastering examples of art, the interpretation of cultural experience in solving artistic, creative and educational tasks, the performance of professional functions of cultural continuity and cultural creativity, which shape the readiness of future art specialists for professional development of self-realization.

As a result of the study of the Professional Standard of a Teacher, as well as scientific literature, based on the key features of the professional and information competence of a music teacher, we clarified the concept of “professional competence of university music students in the field of application of digital art-pedagogical technologies”. The professional competence of university music students in the field of application of digital art-pedagogical technologies is a component of the professional competence of the teacher, which includes:

- knowledge of ways to process various types of data, search and present information, for the purpose of analysis and application in the subject area “Art”;
- the ability to evaluate the content of digital resources in the subject area “Art” in accordance with the assigned educational objectives;
- the use of digital technologies of musical composition and performance with a focus on future professional teaching activities at a university.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the study at this stage, we found that the formed information competence of a specialist is a certain condition for implementation in the professional sphere and is inextricably linked with the implementation of the professional activities of a teacher. The success of completing tasks in the field of professional activity depends on the level of its formation.

As part of the study, the theoretical foundations of the competency-based approach, the essential characteristics and content of the competency-based approach in education were determined.

The main categories of the competency-based approach are analyzed: “competence” and “competence”, their distinctive and key features necessary to continue the research are identified. Based on the analysis of the concept, it was decided to use the concept of “competence” in the course of the study.

Based on the logic of the research, we turned to the study of the term “professional competence” in a broad sense, and also identified the essence and content of “professional competence” of specialists in various fields of activity, including teachers and teacher-musicians.

We also analyzed the concept of “information competence” in various areas of professional activity - within the framework of pedagogical professional activity, and then in the conditions of the professional activity of a teacher-musician. Based on the analysis, we came to the conclusion that the information competence of a specialist is a component of professional competence and the quality of performance of a teacher’s labor functions depends on the level of formation of the information component of professional competence. It was also found that information competence is closely interconnected with knowledge, skills and abilities that allow carrying out professional activities. In this regard, we came to the conclusion that it would be logical to use the term “professional competence of university music students in the field of application of digital art-pedagogical technologies” for further research of the problem posed.

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